

Syn-IDPass: Passport Synthetic Dataset for Presentation Attack Detection

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Abstract

The demand for presentation attack detection (PAD) to identify fraudulent identity documents in remote verification systems has experienced considerable expansion in recent years. This increase is the result of several factors, such as the rise of remote working, online shopping, migration and advances in synthetic imaging. Additionally, an increase in the number of attacks targeting the enrollment process has been noted. Training a PAD system to detect fraudulent identity documents is challenging due to the limited number of available identity documents, as collecting identity passports raises privacy concerns. To address the scarcity of available data, this work proposes a new, realistic ICAO-compliant passport dataset generated using a novel hybrid method that combines synthetic data with open-access information. Experimental evaluation in challenging environments validates the utility of synthetic data. A commercial off-the-shelf PAD algorithm trained on real data computes a detection equal error rate of 19% when using the proposed synthetic dataset for testing¹.

1. Introduction

The need to detect fraudulent identity documents (ID) has risen in the last years due to the increase in remote verification systems related to onboarding processes, pre-enrolment, online purchases, and other uses of smartphones [3]. These processes are typically unsupervised, and the attacker can perform as many attacks as possible or as the system allows.

A remote verification system consists of two branches. The former determines whether the subject in front of the capture device is "live," meaning they are physically present in front of the smartphone. This captured image is a selfie taken under "wild" conditions. The second branch (focus of this work) evaluates the authenticity of each sub-

ject's ID card/passport based on a photo of the document. Approaches in this second category ensure that the ID card/passport is the original one issued by the official service and confirms that it has not been altered, modified or has been used in a replay attack in some way. These algorithms are considered presentation attack detection (PAD) systems that analyse the document's authenticity.

Recently, some initiatives and datasets have been proposed in the literature based mainly on a collection of ID cards and passports [15]. These datasets, nevertheless, often lack the visual quality and structural accuracy necessary to simulate realistic identity forgeries in compliance with standard requirements. For instance, face images in ID cards/passports often present the subject with a hat, sunglasses, rotation, and other conditions that are inappropriate for a genuine document [15]. The low resolution and quantity of the sample are also relevant factors, as is the case with the Prado dataset². The low image quality of these datasets makes them more suitable for evaluating a PAD scheme than for improving its performance through training—they complement the training of the PAD system.

Other constraints of existing datasets lie in the limited number of subjects and images. Many datasets present videos containing only a few subjects, but thousands of attack images of the same subject are generated, resulting in over-fitted and non-generalizable PAD algorithms [12]. The bona fide images also present a challenge because, due to privacy limitations, plastic PVC card-printed images are often used as bona fide, and attacks are generated from these bona fide images. However, the image components on the documents are not aligned with the enrolment rules and present unrealistic scenarios.

It is essential to highlight that the PAD system presents an asymmetrical relationship, because the attacker only needs one well-explained fake ID document, compared to the defenders developing the detection algorithm, who need hundreds or thousands of bona fide images and attack sam-

¹*This dataset is available for research purposes by request.

²<https://nidc.dk/en/Document-Database/ID-databases>

ples to train a PAD system for a new threat.

Motivated by the above limitations, we provide a new passport dataset aligned with ICAO requirements that helps improve the performance and generalizability of ID-card PAD systems without compromising data protection. This dataset was constructed in a hybrid mode, where synthetic images and online information are assembled into an empty ID template. The main contributions of this work are:

- The first hybrid-generated, privacy-preserving synthetic passport dataset that allows a proper training of PAD systems. The passport images (face, text and Machine-readable zone (MRZ) codes) are generated in compliance with ICAO, making the passport more realistic.
- An extensive evaluation of existing face PAD in compliance with the metrics defined in the International Standard ISO/IEC 30107-3 [10] for biometric PAD. This dataset was validated in open-set scenarios and commercial off-the-shelf PAD.
- This dataset is fully available for reproducibility upon request.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Sect. 2 reviews available literature about ID-card PAD. Sect. 3 explains the method to generate the Syn-IDPass, and the experimental setup is defined in Sect. 4. Sect. 5 discusses results obtained, and Sect. 6 concludes this work.

2. Related Work

In the literature, only a few open-access datasets are available, such as MIDV500 [1], MIDV2020 [12], DLC2021 [16], MIDV-Holo [11], Prado and IDNet [6]. Most of them are created from a limited number of subjects and countries, and include many images per subject and attacks or presentation attack instruments (PAI), which limit the generalisation capability of existing PAD subsystems. As expected, the most robust and reliable results have been obtained on private datasets with a high number of subjects, attacks and images per subject [5].

MIDVHolo dataset [11] includes clips featuring documents, such as passports and ID cards, from the fictional country "Utopia." Only artificial documents were used for ethical reasons, which is why "Utopia" serves as a common name for this imaginary country. There are a total of 700 clips in the dataset. It was created to promote research on the topic of automatic hologram detection in video streams.

Benalcazar et al.[2] proposed synthetic datasets for Chilean ID cards based on generative Adversarial networks and artificial textures. The results are very promising, showing that there is still room for improvement to generate

high-quality images with more explicit text. The "Chocolate country" and "Tacoland" were created to demonstrate this technique.

In the KID34K [15] is a dataset created for online identity card fraud Detection. This dataset has ID cards with bona fide and print and screen attacks. No composite images are available. The dataset consists of a total of 34,662 images of 82 ID cards. For 46 subjects who did not exist, they produced 37 registration cards and 45 driver's license cards. Of the 46 subjects, 36 have both types of ID cards. The dataset includes 13,746 genuine, 13,729 screens, and 7,187 print images. However, for the two real datasets, they collected only nine ID cards from nine volunteers and split the ID cards into two sets. The images are not compliant with ICAO requirements. IDNet [6] is a non-ICAO compliant dataset proposed by the Homeland Security Department and includes driver licenses (DL), passports and ID cards from several countries.

Tapia et al. [18] reported the results of the first ID-card PAD competition, highlighting the lack of images to train robust PAD systems and the lower capability to infer different countries, which results in low performance and makes PAD schemes infeasible for real applications.

In addition, Gonzalez et al. [5] demonstrated that the performance of PAD systems significantly improved when private datasets with a large number of samples were used for training. However, new developments are conditioned to use public datasets rather than private ones.

3. Proposed Method

To address the lack of public datasets, the following describes a process for generating fake passports using a new hybrid method that incorporates freely available data and synthetic facial images. This enables us to obtain visually convincing passport facial images that meet ICAO requirements and have been validated using face image quality assessment software.

The whole process is structured into five core components: (1) template normalization from layered Photoshop files (Sect. 3.1), (2) generation of structured subject metadata (Sect. 3.2), (3) biometric image selection and filtering (Sect. 3.3), (4) multimodal compositing of image layers (Sect. 3.4), and (5) reconstruction of complex visual overlays such as logos and patterns (Sect. 3.5). While the implementation described here targets Polish passports, the pipeline generalises to other national formats with some adjustments in the JSON configuration files. Figure 1 shows all the areas of interest in one passport.

3.1. ID-Template Recovery and Normalisation

Passport templates used in this work were sourced from layered Photoshop (PSD) files that are publicly available via online websites or generated internally from an original

ing an open-source library ⁴, configured to match the ICAO 9303 specification. Character positioning, kerning offsets (distance between letters), and font metrics were modelled manually based on inspection, particularly for the non-machine-readable zones, which use country-specific and often non-standard fonts ⁵.

All subject data and layout parameters were specified via country-specific configuration files. These files define not only the location of text fields and biometric images, but also document-level rendering parameters such as font families, kerning coefficients, colour values, transparency levels, and character alignment rules.

3.3. Biometric Data Selection and Filtering

Facial portraits were sourced from the ONOT synthetic dataset [4], which provides multiple synthetic face images per subject. However, the uncontrolled generation process yields images with variable pose, resolution, and artefacts. To approximate ICAO compliance, we developed a custom filtering pipeline based on the following criteria, which were validated by Open Face Image Quality (OFIQ) [14]:

- Minimum face bounding box resolution
- Minimum relative eye-to-eye pixel distance
- Minimum relative margin from eye center to image edge
- Sharpness according to OFIQ

No manual selection was performed; instead, the top three-ranked images per subject were retained. Face detection and mesh estimation were performed using MediaPipe, while final segmentation was conducted in Adobe Photoshop due to its superior handling of edge blending and texture preservation in our tests. Face cropping was done according to the ICAO standard 9303. Mask and face mesh were saved and used in the later generation of the fake passport ⁶.

Signatures were drawn from the OHSDA datasets [17]. All biometric assets were preprocessed to remove backgrounds, with binary masks stored for compositing. Examples of the process are depicted in Fig. 2. Fingerprints were generated (for Argentine or Colombian passports) using SFinGe and randomly assigned to each subject.

Figure 2. Example of signature extraction process. Left to Right: Base image from the dataset. Binarise image. Remove background, add to passport.

3.4. Layer Compositing Pipeline

Each synthetic passport was generated by compositing subject-specific data onto the cleaned ID-template. The placement and ordering of visual elements are controlled via layer masks and the rendering sequence defined in the configuration file.

A range of post-processing operations is supported by the framework, of which the following were applied in the Polish passport setting:

- **Edge blurring:** applied along mask boundaries to prevent hard seams.
- **Opacity tuning:** transparency levels are adjusted per-layer based on empirical inspection of authentic documents.
- **Character tuning:** Character-level layout corrections are applied when the selected font does not fully match the visual appearance of the reference. This includes manual positioning, per-character kerning, and the application of predefined layout transformations.

Text fields are rendered using the visual characteristics extracted from the reference ID template. These include font type, character spacing, rotation, and baseline curvature.

3.5. Pattern and Logo Processing

Visual elements such as holograms, emblems, and security patterns are either extracted from the template or reconstructed manually. When available, pattern layers were reused directly. Otherwise, we applied classical computer vision techniques (e.g., contour detection, colour thresholding) to extract patterns semi-automatically.

Figure 3. Detailed logo and pattern information created to follow the pattern of the Polish passport.

⁴<https://pypi.org/project/mrz/>

⁵<https://github.com/Arg0s1080/mrz>

⁶<https://www.icao.int/publications/pages/publication.aspx?docnum=9303>

Figure 4. Basic steps for fake passport generation. Left to right: Empty template, intermediate state with demographic text, and final composition with biometric image.

Figure 5. Example of three fake passport generations for the following countries. Left to right: Spain, Poland, Portugal.

In challenging cases—where the template did not provide a cleanly segmented logo layer, and all available reference examples showed the logo partially occluded by text, biometric data, or other overlays—segmentation was performed manually using GIMP. Colours were corrected via palette estimation, and placement masks were constructed to guide compositing logic. Fig. 3 depicts an example applied to the logo adaptation of the face picture.

Three empty templates were used to generate fake Passports belonging to Spain, Portugal, and Poland. All the passports generated follow the original pattern presented by each country.

Figure 4 illustrates three passport images that depict the complete process, from an empty template to the final version.

Figure 5 presents an example of each passport generated for Spain, Poland and Portugal.

3.6. Synthetic Dataset: Syn-IDPass

Using the above methodology, 1,000 images were automatically generated for each country, resulting in a total of 3,000 images, which are considered as pseudo bona fide. For the passport images of the three countries, both print and screen images were manually created, one by one, as attacks. For printed attacks, four images per sheet were placed on glossy 180-gram paper to maintain the official size at 600 dpi and simulate the original passport materials.

For screen attack, the images generated were displayed

on a screen and captured using a smartphone. In total, the dataset comprises 9,000 images, divided into 3,000 bona fide (Passport-generated), 3,000 manually printed attacks captured using two different smartphones, and 3,000 manually screened attacks captured from Dell laptop screens. Examples of pseudo bona fide images and PAI species (print and screen attacks) are shown in Fig. 6

4. Experimental Setup

This work aims to evaluate the feasibility of the generated a dataset to train PAD algorithms that can detect both known and unknown attacks. For this purpose, two experiments, an intra-dataset and a leave-one-out (LOO) protocol, are considered for evaluating our passport synthetic datasets. The intra-dataset scenario defines a known-attack scenario where the PAI species used in the fabrication of training data remain the same for fabricating testing data.

For the leave-one-out scenarios, passports belonging to two countries are used for training, while the documents from the remaining country are employed for testing. The full dataset for intra-dataset was divided into 60% for training, 20% for validation and 20% for test. For the leave-one-out protocol, the 3,000 images belonging to Poland (pseudo bona fide, print and screen) were used as a test set, and Spain and Portugal were used as training and validation subsets. The print and screen attacks were evaluated separately.

Figure 6. Examples of bona fide, printed and screen images generated for PAD system.

4.1. PAD Subsystem and Implementation Details

As PAD can be seen as a binary supervised task, methods can be trained to provide a binary classification. Therefore, we selected existing networks: DenseNet121 [9], MobileNetV3-large [8], ResNet34 and ResNet101 [7]. Additionally, a Swin-Transformer [13] was employed, leveraging the capabilities of Vision Transformers that distinguish it from traditional Deep learning models. The models evaluated are: SwinT-Base, SwinT-Small, and SwinT-Large. All the models were trained using SGD and Adam optimisers. Different learning rates were explored using a grid search from $1e-3$ to $1e-6$. The lr value of $1e-3$ and 50 epochs achieved the best results. The input size was adapted according to each model for deep learning and visual transformer models. Therefore, images are resized to 224×224 .

In the case of SwinT models, the most detailed configuration is described. The patch size division that makes a stronger classifier with the following configuration: image-size = 224×224 , patch-size = 4, num-channels = 3, embed-dim = 96, depths = [2, 2, 6, 2], num-heads = [3, 6, 12, 24], window-size = 7, mlp-ratio = 4.0, drop-path-rate = 0.1, hidden-act = 'gelu', initializer-range = 0.02, layer-norm-eps = $1e-05$ encoder-stride = 3.

The parameters for all SwinT are selected according to: SwinT-B, SwinT-S, and SwinT-L model sizes, whose complexities are increased from baseline SwinT-B by $\times 0.5$, $\times 1$, and $\times 2$. Window size M is set to 7 by default, and the query dimension of each head (as multi-head attention is used) is 32 for all these models.

4.2. Evaluation Metrics

The ISO/IEC 30107-3 standard [10] presents methodologies and metrics for evaluating the performance of PAD algorithms for biometric systems. The APCER metric measures the proportion of attack presentations—for each different PAI—incorrectly classified as bona fide presentations. This metric is calculated for each PAI, where the worst-case scenario is considered. Eq. 1 details how to compute the APCER metric, in which the value of N_{PAIS} corresponds to the number of attack presentation images, where RES_i for the i th image is 1 if the algorithm classifies it as

an attack presentation, or 0 if it is classified as a bona fide presentation (real image).

$$APCER_{PAIS} = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N_{PAIS}} \right) \sum_{i=1}^{N_{PAIS}} RES_i \quad (1)$$

Additionally, the BPCER metric measures the proportion of bona fide presentations mistakenly classified as attack presentations, or the ratio of false rejections to total bona fide attempts. The BPCER metric is formulated according to Eq. 2, where N_{BF} corresponds to the number of bona fide presentation images, and RES_i takes identical values of those of the APCER metric.

$$BPCER = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{BF}} RES_i}{N_{BF}} \quad (2)$$

These metrics effectively measure the degree to which the algorithm confuses presentations of attack images with bona fide images and vice versa. The APCER and BPCER metrics depend on a decision threshold.

5. Experiment, Results and Discussion

To reach the above-defined goal, we present the algorithm's performance for the intra-dataset (Sect. 5.1) and leave-one-out (Sect. 5.2) evaluation.

5.1. Experiment 1 - Intra-dataset

In order to show the generalisation capabilities of deep learning models, we evaluated five classifiers trained from scratch using ImageNet weights as a baseline on two classes, bona fide and attacks. The two best methods are highlighted in a grey background.

Fig. 7 shows the DET curves for Intra-dataset (left) and leave-one-out protocol (middle and right). The three countries, Spain, Portugal, and Poland, were used in intra-datasets and divided into two classes, bona fide versus attacks. The best results are obtained by DenseNet121 for the DL models and SwinT-L for the Vision Transformer models. Conversely, the ResNet34 obtained the worst results in terms of D-EER.

Figure 7. DET curve shows the results for a deep learning and SwinT classifiers considering the three countries. Left: in intra-dataset evaluation. Middle: LOO print attack as a test. Right: LOO screen attacks as a test.

Table 1. PAD summary results. Intra and LOO scenarios considering Portugal and Spain as the training set. The Polish passport images are used as a test set.

Models	Intra				LOO - Printed				LOO - Screen			
	D-EER (%)	BPCER10 (%)	BPCER20 (%)	BPCER100 (%)	D-EER (%)	BPCER10 (%)	BPCER20 (%)	BPCER100 (%)	D-EER (%)	BPCER10 (%)	BPCER20 (%)	BPCER100 (%)
Deep Learning												
DenseNet121	1.39	0.3	0.53	2.39	1.79	0.0	0.0	7.20	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
MobileNetV3-1	3.54	1.03	2.16	16.33	0.81	0.0	0.0	0.69	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ResNet34	11.0	13.33	28.51	60.03	11.36	12.55	21.16	53.72	2.31	0.93	1.16	4.41
ResNet101	1.83	0.33	0.67	3.16	2.78	1.62	2.55	9.06	1.15	0.0	0.0	2.09
Vision Transformers												
Swin_v2_b	2.20	0.33	1.44	3.67	3.36	0.46	2.09	7.20	1.73	0.0	0.46	15.81
Swin_v2_s	2.10	0.17	0.34	6.17	6.72	3.25	13.02	31.16	0.46	0.0	0.0	0.23
Swin_v2_t	0.70	0.0	0.0	0.17	3.13	0.23	1.86	10.46	0.69	0.0	0.0	0.69

5.2. Experiment 2 - Leave-one-out

For the LOO protocol, we applied the following order for Spain, Portugal, and Poland passports, considering print and screen attacks. For the training process, Spain and Portugal were used for training and validation, while Poland was used for testing. The attacks were evaluated separately to emulate unknown attacks.

For the LOO protocol, the evaluation was made considering bona fide versus print and screen attacks. Fig.7(middle) shows the results for the LOO for the Poland passport as a test set and Portugal and Spain as a train set, considering a printed attack using it as an unknown attack. The model with the best results was MobileNetV3, and the worst was ResNet34.

Fig. 7(right) shows the results for the LOO for screen attack using it as an unknown attack. The model with the best results was SwinV2-S, and the worst was ResNet34.

Tab.1 presents a summary of the results for both protocols, including three different operational points: BPCER10, BPCER20, and BPCER100, for both traditional deep learning classifiers and Swin-T based on Vision-Transformers. As expected, the intra-dataset scenario yielded a low D-EER because bona fide and attack samples were generated using the same techniques. For the attacks, the screen scenarios are identified as less complex compared to the printed ones.

5.3. Benchmark with State of the art

In order to evaluate whether the traditional ID-card PAD system is vulnerable concerning the generated images, all the passport images generated were used to benchmark two state-of-the-art systems.

The **first model** trained was based on a subset used in [5], which contains genuine Chilean ID Cards for training, considering print and attack scenarios.

The **second model** trained was based on the IDNet dataset for training [6], which includes a passports subset with printed and screen scenarios, among others.

Fig. 8 shows the DET curve results for the three datasets generated by countries that include printed and screen attacks. As depicted, the generated passports are very challenging, even for the two stronger classifiers aligned with our goal. For both evaluations, the Polish passport (black line) is identified as more complex than the Spanish passport (blue line) and the Portuguese passport (red line). The D-EER is 17.35% for PAD-ID and over 23.5% IDNet, respectively.

It is essential to highlight that real systems evaluate ID Cards and Passport images in the same pipeline. The companies usually do not generate separate models for each one.

Figure 8. The DET curve shows the results for three countries generated when evaluated in a state-of-the-art classifier using the Chilean ID card and IDNet-Passport sets.

5.4. Commercial PAD for ID Cards

The generation of the passport was developed from an ID template and follows the ICAO standard to obtain a more realistic version. The lack of bona fide passport images to evaluate the difference between the genuine and synthetic versions makes it impossible to get any similarity metrics. Motivated by this limitation, we required that our passport images be assessed by a private biometric company that has a commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) PAD product⁷. A subset of 1,000 Polish synthetic passports, 1,000 print and 1,000 screen were evaluated. The subset yielded a D-EER of 19.0% and BPCER10 of 21.0%. These results validated our Syn-IDPass dataset as an alternative to improve the generalisation capabilities.

6. Conclusion

The Syn-IDPass dataset presents a good challenge, and it's a valuable dataset that can be used to improve the PAD system based on passports or ID cards. The method utilising SwinTransformer achieved the best results, highlighting the effectiveness of dividing images into small patches based on attention map layers. This approach enables the network to focus on specific areas, thereby enhancing its ability to detect changes within each region.

In contrast, while deep learning convolution techniques can capture texture changes at various resolutions, this capability is insufficient to enhance the PAD system.

As future work, we will expand this research and dataset to include other countries, as well as new attacks such as composite and plastic.

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⁷The third-party company did not agree to disclose the name.

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